

STOCHASTIC FRACTAL SEARCH

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Abstract. In this paper, simulates the updating position of each agent based on some statistical approaches. To verify the performance of our algorithm, some benchmark functions including spectrum classic, modern and engineering design functions which are commonly used in literature, have been used.

Keywords: Iterated function systems, strange attractors L-systems, Finite subdivision rules, random fractals, diffusing process, updating process, Levy flight, Gaussian distributions.

1. Introduction.

The property of an object or quantity which explains self-similarity on all scales, in a somewhat technical sense, is called fractal. The term of “fractal” comes from the Latin word *fractus* which means “broken” or “fractured”, and it was first used by Benoit Mandelbrot in 1975. Mandelbrot also tried to use the concept of fractal theories to describe geometric patterns in nature .

Developing research in this area, the example list of fractals including structures from microscopic aggregates to the cluster of galaxies has been become very long. Far-from-equilibrium growth phenomena are an important field where fractals observe, and are engaged to many fields of science and technology. Some examples for such processes include dendritic solidification in an undercooled medium, viscous fingering which is observed when a viscous fluid is injected into a more viscous one, and electrodepositing of ions onto an electrode .

Typically, to generate a fractal shape, some common methods such as: Iterated function systems , Strange attractors L-systems, Finite subdivision rules and Random fractals are used. Based on the fractal characteristics, our new metaheuristic method inspires random fractals grown by Diffusion Limited Aggregation (DLA) method concept as a successful search algorithm in both accuracy and time consumption.

Fractal Search uses three simple rules to find a solution:

1. Each particle has an electrical potential energy.
2. Each particle diffuses, and causes some other random particles to be created, and the energy of the seed particle is divided among generated particles.
3. Only few of the best particles remain in each generation, and the rest of the particles are disregarded.

2. Stochastic fractal search.

Although Fractal Search performs well in finding the solution, but this approach suffers from some disadvantages. The main one is having a lot of parameters that need to be well addressed, and the other is that information exchange does not occur among particles. Exchanging information among all participating points in the group is an attempt to speed up convergence to minimum. In FS, no information exchange has turned up between individuals, and, it is essential that the search is performed independently, so, this situation is rectified in our new algorithm by adding a phase called updating process. On the other hand, since Fractal Search is a dynamic algorithm in the sense that the number of agents in the algorithm is modified, we have faced a trade-off between accuracy and time consumption. Therefore, to tackle the mentioned problems, we introduce another version of Fractal Search called Stochastic Fractal Search (SFS).

Two main processes occurred in the SFS algorithm are: The diffusing process and the updating process. In the first process, similar to Fractal Search, each particle diffuses around its current position to satisfy intensification (exploitation) property. This process increases the chance of finding the global minima, and also prevents being trapped in the local minima. In the latter process, the algorithm simulates how a point in the group updates its position based on the position

of other points in the group. Unlike the diffusing phase in FS which causes a dramatic increase in the number of participating points, we consider a static diffusion process for SFS. It means that the best generated particle from the diffusing process is the only particle that is considered, and the rest of the particles are discarded. In addition to efficient exploration of the problem space, SFS uses some random methods as updating processes. In other word, updating process in SFS leads us to diversification (exploration) properties in metaheuristic algorithms.

To create new particles from the diffusion procedure, two statistical methods called Levy flight and Gaussian are investigated. Preliminary studies over taking advantage of Levy and Gaussian distributions separately show, however, that although Levy flight converges faster than Gaussian walk in a few generations; Gaussian walk is more promising than Levy flight in finding global minima. Therefore, unlike Fractal Search which uses the Levy flight distribution, Gaussian distribution is the only random walk employed in the DLA growth process of SFS. Generally, a series of Gaussian walks participating in the diffusion process have been listed in the following equations:

$$GW_1 = \text{Gaussian}(\mu_{PB}, \sigma) + (\varepsilon xBP - \varepsilon' xP_i) \quad (1)$$

$$GW_2 = \text{Gaussian}(\mu_P, \sigma) \quad (2)$$

where ε and ε' are uniformly distributed random numbers restricted to $[0, 1]$. BP and P_i are denoted as the position of the best point and the i th point in the group, respectively. The first two Gaussian parameters are μ_{BP} and σ where μ_{BP} is exactly equal to $|BP|$. The two the latter parameters are μ_P and σ where μ_P is equal to $|P_i|$. With consideration of Gaussian parameters, the standard deviation is computed by Eq

$$\sigma = \left| \frac{\log(g)}{g} x(P_i - PB) \right| \quad (3)$$

To encourage a more localized search as individuals, and get closer to the solution, the term $\frac{\log(g)}{g}$ is used in order to decrease the size of Gaussian jumps, as the number of generation increases.

Assume a global optimization problem with dimension D is at hand. Therefore, each denoted individual considered to solve the problem has been built based on a D -dimensional vector. During the initialization process, each point is initialized randomly based on problem constrains by prescribing minimum and maximum bounds. The initialization equation of the j th point, P_i , is addressed as follows:

$$P_i = LB + \varepsilon x(UB - LB) \quad (4)$$

where LB and UB are the lower and the upper problem constrained vectors, respectively. As stated in previous equations, ε is a uniformly distributed random number which is restricted to $[0, 1]$ continuous area. After initializing all points, the fitness function of each point is computed to attain the best point (BP) among all points. According to the exploitation property in the diffusion procedure, all points have roamed around their current position to exploit problem search space. On the other hand, two statistical procedures aimed to increase the better space exploration are considered due to the exploration property. The first statistical procedure performs on each individual vector index, and the second statistical method is then applied to all points.

For the first statistical procedure, at first, all the points are ranked based on the value of the fitness function. Each point i in the group is then given a probability value which obeys a simple uniform distribution as following equation:

$$P_{a_j} = \frac{\text{rank}(P_i)}{N} \quad (5)$$

where $\text{rank}(P_i)$ is consider as the rank of point P_i among the other points in the group, and N is used as the number of all points in the group. In fact, Eq. (5) wants to state that the better the point, the higher the probability. This equation is used to increase the chance of changing the position of points which have not obtained a good solution. On the other hand, the chance of passing good solutions in the next generation will increase. For each point P_i in group, based on whether or not

the condition $Pa_i < \varepsilon$ is satisfied, the j th component of P_i , is updated according to Eq. (6), otherwise it remains unchanged.

$$P_i'(j) = P_i(j) - \varepsilon \times (P_t(j) - P_i(j)) \quad (6)$$

where P_i' is the new modified position of P_i . P_r and P_t are random selected points in the group, ε is the random number selected from the uniform distribution in the continuous space $[0, 1]$.

Regarding to the first statistical procedure which is carried out on the components of the points, the second statistical change is aimed to change the position of a point considering the position of other points in the group. This property improves the quality of exploration, and it satisfies the diversification property. Before starting the second procedure, once again, all points obtained from the first statistical procedure are ranked based on Eq. (5). Similar to the first statistical process, if the condition $Pa_i < \varepsilon$ is held for a new point P_i' , the current position of P_i' is modified according to Eqs. (7), (8), otherwise no update occurs. Eqs. (7), (8) are presented as follows:

$$P_i'' = P_i' - \varepsilon \times P_i' - BP \quad \varepsilon' \leq 0.5 \quad (7)$$

$$P_i'' = P_i' + \varepsilon \times P_i' - P_r' \quad \varepsilon' > 0.5 \quad (8)$$

where P_r' and P_t' are random selected points obtained from the first procedure, and ε' are random numbers generated by the Gaussian Normal distribution. The new point P_i'' is replaced by P_i' if its fitness function value is better than P_i' . The standard Stochastic Fractal Search can be described as follows:

Stochastic Fractal Search Pseudo Algorithm.

Initialize a population of N points

While $g < \text{maximum generation}$ or (stop criterion) **Do**

{

For each Point P_i in the system **Do**

{

Call Diffusion Process with the following process:

{

$q =$ (maximum considered number of diffusion).

For $j = 1$ to q **Do**

{

If (user applies the first Gaussian walk to solve the problem)

{

Create a new point based on Eq. [href="#e0055" \(1\)](#).

}

Else (user sets the second Gaussian Walks to solve the problem)

{

Create a new point based on Eq. [href="#e0060" \(2\)](#).

}

}

}

Call Updating Process with the following process

{

Fist Updating Process:

First, all points are ranked based on Eq. [\(3\)](#).

For each Point P_i in the system **Do**

{

For each component j in P_i **Do**

{

```

If rand[0,1] ≥ Pai
{
  Update the component in based on Eq. (6).
}
Else
{
  Do nothing.
}
}

```

Second Updating Process:

Once again, all points obtained by the first update process are ranked based on Eq. (5).

For each new point P_i' in the system **Do**

```

{
If (rand[0,1] ≥ Pai')
{
  Update the position based on Eqs. (7), (8).
}
Else
{
  Do nothing.
}
}
}

```

3. Conclusions.

In this paper, simulates the updating position of each agent based on some statistical approaches. To verify the performance of our algorithm, some benchmark functions including spectrum classic, modern and engineering design functions which are commonly used in literature, have been used. Surprisingly, obtained results show that our new algorithm clearly outperforms some well-known algorithms from literature. The proposed system can contribute to answering many fundamental and practical problems in many fields such as machine learning, bioinformatics, image processing and generally any field in need of optimization. Improving the classification performance, being considered as a powerful feature selection, determining RNA secondary predictions, finding high order SNP interactions, and improving image segmentation are some possible applications contemplated as future studies. However, further research is required to examine the efficiencies of the proposed algorithm on other real world and large scale optimization problems.

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